

A Comparative Study of Bibliometric Characteristics of the *DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology* and *Annals of Library and Information Studies*

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Abstract

The study presents a comparative analysis of citations of articles published in DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology (DJLIT) and Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS) during 2017 to 2019 and the citations received by these articles during 2017 to 2020 (June) using Google Scholar. The study reveals that DJLIT published more papers per issue than ALIS and the papers of DJLIT have received more number of citations than the papers of ALIS. The study also reveals that both impact factor and immediacy index of DJLIT are higher than of ALIS. The study also lists the highly cited papers/authors during 2017 – 2020 (June) in both the journals.

Keywords: Bibliometrics; Bibliometric Analysis; DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology and Annals of Library and Information Studies; Indian LIS Journals.

1. Introduction

Citation analysis is a method of determining the importance or impact of an author or a publication by counting the number of times it was cited by others. It involves the examination of the frequency, patterns, and graphs of citations to documents. Verma (1994) defines “citation analysis as a technique of bibliometrics study of literature, based on the principle that there is some degree of relationship between the citing and cited articles. The frequency of the cited documents appearing in a number of citing articles is, in some measure, an indication of its influence or impact on the subject. Ranking of periodicals based on such frequencies has its manifold usages both for the scientists of the field and the librarians. The technique of citation is largely statistical and is used for arranging those cited materials in some kind of rank to study their relative importance”. Measures such as impact factor, half life, immediacy index, and a set of other indexes like the h-index and its other variant forms have been

formulated as quantitative measures of the impact of papers and authors.

The Impact Factor (IF) was devised by Eugene Garfield, the founder of the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI) in Philadelphia, as a measure of the impact of scientific journals. The IF of a journal during the year Y is calculated as the ratio the number of times the contents of the journal was cited during the previous two years that is Y-1 and Y-2 and the total number of citable items published in the journal during the same period. For instance, if a journal published 120 articles in previous two years and the articles in the journal got cited 90 times in the current year, then the Impact Factor of that particular journal in the current year will be $90/120 = 0.75$. Immediacy Index of a journal is the average number of times the articles in it got cited in the same year it is published. The journal Immediacy Index indicates how quickly articles in a journal are cited. The

present study is a citation analysis of two prominent journals in Library and Information Science (LIS) published from India, the *Annals of Library and Information Studies* (ALIS) and the *DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology* (DJLIT) taking the contents of the journals during the three years 2017 to 2019.

2. Review of Literature

In the past, several studies dealing with bibliometric analyses of journals have been reported, which have explored the authorship pattern of published articles, institutional affiliation of contributing authors, average length of articles, the number of contributions in relation to specific subject areas and the characteristics of references appended. For instance, Deshmukh (2011) has made an analysis of 4141 citations appended to articles published in volumes 44 to 57 of the ASIS. The source journal is found to be most cited. The half life of LIS literature is found to be 9 years for journals and 14 years for books respectively. Kumar & Moorthy (2011) and Bansal (2013) have made a bibliometric analysis of *DJLIT*. A bibliometric analysis of articles published during 2002-2012 in ALIS has been undertaken by Pandita (2013).

Asok Kumar et al (2014) trace the historical development of DJLIT which was started as a newsletter and later developed into learned research journal. Garg & Bebi (2014) analysed citations appended to articles published in ALIS and DJLIT during 2010 to 2013. A scientometric analysis of DJLIT for 2010 to 2014 was done by Imran Khan (2016). A paper by Batcha et al (2018) analyses the pattern of growth of the research output published in DJLIT, pattern of authorship, author productivity, and subjects covered in the papers over the period 2013-2017. Renjith (2018) attempted to highlight the citation output of research articles in DJLIT published during the period 2006-2015 based on Google Scholar. The study proved that the level of citation is not constant and the citation output differs significantly with their publication year. Lamba & Madhusudhan (2019) analysed 928 full-text research articles retrieved from DJLIT for the period of 1981–2018 using

Latent Dirichlet Allocation and tagged the articles with the modelled topics. 50 core topics were identified throughout the period of 38 years whereas only 26 topics were unique in nature. The topics of high preference include Bibliometrics, ICT, information retrieval, and user studies. Further, Spain and Taiwan showed common research trends and areas as India at the same time India was found to have quite distinct research interests from America and China. Renjith (2019) in another paper examined the authorship pattern and citation level of i10 cited papers of DJLIT based on Google Scholar data. The study established that citations of i10 cited papers are equally distributed in different authorship patterns and no association between authorship pattern and level of citations.

Even though several bibliometric studies are there centring DJLIT and ALIS, studies on the citations received by the papers in the journals in recent years are seen lacking. Hence the author attempts to look into the citations to DJLIT and ALIS as reflected in Google Scholar.

3. Objectives of the Study

- To find out the average number of articles published per issue in DJLIT and ALIS during 2017-2019.
- To find out the number of articles published in the two journals during 2017-2019 and the citations obtained by them during 2017-2020 (June).
- To determine the extent of citations obtained by the journals.
- To identify highly cited authors/papers.
- To calculate Immediacy Index for 2017– 2019 and impact factor of the two journals for the year 2019.

4. Methodology

The data for the study have been collected from the respective websites of the journals for the years 2017-2019 (three years). Citations for the published articles were examined using Google Scholar for the period 2017-2020 (June). The results were tabulated and analysed to meet the objectives mentioned above.

5. Discussion

5.1. Source Journals

5.1.1 The Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS):

The journal started under the name Annals of Library Science in 1954 by the former Indian National Scientific Documentation Centre (INSDOC), now NISCAIR, as a quarterly publication. The title of journal was changed to Annals of Library and Information Studies in 2001. The journal is available in open access at its website nopr.niscair.res.in/handle/123456789/66 from volume 1, issue number 1 (1954) onwards.

5.1.2. DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology (DJLIT):

The journal was started in 1980 by Defence Scientific Information and Documentation Centre (DESIDOC) as a four-page newsletter under the title DESIDOC Bulletin and it published mainly the activities of DESIDOC. In 1985, the bulletin started publishing articles on IT applications to the discipline of LIS. It was renamed as DESIDOC Bulletin of Information Technology (DBIT) in 1992.

Since then, it is being published bi-monthly. In 2008, DBIT became a primary research journal and was renamed as DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology (DJLIT).

5.2. Number of Articles Published and Citations Scored

Table 1 indicates the number of articles published in DJLIT and ALIS during the three years covered in the study. The total of papers in the two journals is 173 and 80 respectively. The average number of articles published per issue during the period works out to 9.61 for DJLIT and 6.66 for ALIS. As it is evident, the average number of articles in DJLIT is more than that in ALIS.

Table 2 presents the data on the number of articles published in the two journals during 2017-2019 and the number of citations obtained by them during 2017 – 2020 (June). Average number of citations obtained per paper during these three years is 3.26 for DJLIT and 2.17 for ALIS. Thus, the average number of citations obtained by DJLIT is slightly more than ALIS.

Table 1 : Average Number of Articles per Issue

Year	DJLIT		ALIS	
	No. of articles	Average no. per issue	No. of articles	Average no. per issue
2017	58	9.66	32	8
2018	61	10.16	28	7
2019	54	9	20	5
Total	173	9.61	80	6.66

Table 2 : Year-wise Distribution of Articles and their Citations

Year	DJLIT			ALIS		
	No. of Articles	No. of Citations	Citations per Article	No. of Articles	No. of Citations	Citations per Article
2017	58	338	5.82	32	118	3.68
2018	61	174	2.85	28	44	1.57
2019	54	52	0.96	20	12	0.6
Total	173	564	3.26	80	174	2.17

5.3. Extent of Citations

Table 3 presents distribution of papers in the two journals in the increasing order of the number of citations per paper. It reveals the extent of citations received by the two journals. The number of citations per paper is in the range of 0 to 26 for

DJLIT and 0 to 18 for ALIS. While the 173 papers in DJLIT bagged 564 citations, the 80 papers in ALIS have received 174 citations. The average number of citations per paper comes to 3.26 and 2.175 respectively. The highest number of citations is 26 for DJLIT and 18 for ALIS.

Table 3 : Distribution of Papers in DJLIT and ALIS Based on Number of Citations per Paper

Number of Citations per Paper	DJLIT			ALIS		
	No. of Articles	Total No. of Citations	Percentage	No. of Articles	Total No. of Citations	Percentage
0	48	0	27.7457	30	0	37.5
1	28	28	16.185	18	18	22.5
2	22	44	12.7168	10	20	12.5
3	16	48	9.24855	3	9	3.75
4	18	72	10.4046	6	24	7.5
5	10	50	5.78035	5	25	6.25
6	8	48	4.62428	1	6	1.25
7	3	21	1.7341	3	21	3.75
8	2	16	1.15607			
9	5	45	2.89017			
10	2	20	1.15607	1	10	1.25
11	3	33	1.7341	1	11	1.25
12	2	24	1.15607	1	12	1.25
13	2	26	1.15607			
18	1	18	0.57803	1	18	1.25
22	1	22	0.57803			
23	1	23	0.57803			
26	1	26	0.57803			
Total	173	564	100	80	174	100

Out of total articles published by DJLIT and ALIS during 2017 to 2019, 48 articles (28%) of DJLIT and 30 articles (37.5%) of ALIS did not get any citation. It indicates that the proportion of uncited articles of ALIS is more than that in DJLIT. The table also indicates that 13 articles (7.5%) of DJLIT and 4 articles (5%) were cited 10 or more times.

These two tables indicate that 13 articles in DJLIT and 4 articles in ALIS were cited 10 times and above. Data presented in Tables 4 and 5 for highly cited authors indicate that out of the 17 highly cited authors/papers, 16 papers were published in 2017 and only 1 paper in 2018. Papers published in 2017 received more citations as these have a bigger citation window than papers published in later years.

Tables 4 and 5 list the papers which were cited 10 times or more during 2017-2020 (June).

Table 4: Highly Cited Papers of DJLIT

Sl. No.	Name of the Authors and Title of the Paper	No. of Citations
1	Garg, K. C & Sharma, Chetan. Bibliometrics of Library and Information Science research in India during 2004-2015, 37 (3) 2017, 221-227.	26
2	Tripathi, Manorama & Shukla, Archana; Sonkar, Sharad Kumar. Research Data Management Practices in University libraries: A study, 37 (6) 2017, 417-424.	23
3	Md Sohail & Shakil Ahmad. Use of Electronic Resources and Services by Faculty Members and Students of Fiji National University, 37 (3) 2017, 165-171.	22
4	Mallya, Jyothi & Lakshminarayanan, Sethumadhavan. Factors Influencing Usage of Internet for Academic Purposes Using Technology Acceptance Model, 37 (2) 2017, 119-124.	18
5	Mohd Shoaib Ansari & Tripathi, Aditya. Use of WhatsApp for Effective Delivery of Library and Information Services, 37 (5) 2017, 360-365.	13
6	Mondal, Dhiman; Kanamadi, Satish & Das, Kingsuk. Contribution by Indian Authors in Foreign Origin Library and Information Science Journals during 2006-2015: A Scientometrics Study, 37 (6) 2017, 396-402.	13
7	Bapte, Vishal Dattatray. DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology (DJLIT): A Bibliometric Analysis of Cited References, 37 (4) 2017, 264-269.	12
8	Gupta, Parul & Margam, Madhusudhan. RFID Technology in Libraries: A Review of Literature of Indian Perspective, 37 (1) 2017, 58-63.	12
9	Khanna, Sunaina. [et. al.]. Scientometric Analysis of the Research Output of Physics and Astronomy of Guru Nanak Dev University during 2006-15, 37 (5) 2017, 337-345.	11
10	Nanda, Archita. Use and Awareness of E-journals by the Faculty and Research Scholars of Veer Surendra Sai University of Technology: A Study, 37 (4) 2017, 274-280.	11
11	Verma, Manoj Kumar & Brahma, Krishna. Websites of Central Universities in North East India: A Webometric Analysis, 37 (3) 2017, 186-191.	11
12	Mallya, Jyothi & Patwardhan, Vidya. Hospitality Students' Perception of College Library Service Quality: Importance- Performance Analysis, 38 (2) 2018, 125-131.	10
13	Margam, Madhusudhan & Saleeq Ahmad Dar. Mobile Information Services and Initiatives in University Libraries: A New Way of Delivering Information, 37 (2) 2017, 109-118	10

Table 5: Highly Cited Papers of ALIS

Sl. No.	Name of the Authors and Title of the Paper	No. of citations
1	Verma, Manoj Kumar & Brahma, Krishna. A webometric analysis of National Libraries' websites in South Asia, 64 (2) 2017, 116-124.	18
2	Garg, K. C. & Tripathi, H. K. Bibliometrics and scientometrics in India: An overview of studies during 1995-2014 Part I: Indian publication output and its citation impact, 64 (1) 2017, 28-36.	12
3	Suresh, Kumar P K. Author productivity and the application of Lotka's Law in LIS publications, 64 (4) 2017, 234-241.	11
4	Dhawan, S.M.; Gupta, B.M. & Gupta, Ritu. Mobile computing: a scientometric assessment of global publications output, 64 (3) 2017, 172-180.	10

5.4. Impact Factor

Table 6 presents the Impact Factor of the two journals, DJLIT and ALIS for the year 2019, estimated based on the number of papers published in 2017 to 2018 and the number citations received by these papers in 2019. The values are 2.07 and 1.22 for DJLIT and ALIS respectively. It

indicates that the impact factor of DJLIT is higher than that of ALIS.

5.5. Immediacy Index

Immediacy Index of the two journals estimated for 2017, 2018 and 2019 are given in table 7. It is observed that the values for DJLIT are higher than that for ALIS.

Table 6 : Impact Factor of DJLIT and ALIS

Sl. No.	Parameter	DJLIT	ALIS
1	Number of papers published in 2017 and 2018	119	60
2	Number of citations received in the year 2019	246	73
3	Impact Factor in 2019	2.07	1.22

Table 7 : Immediacy Index of DJLIT and ALIS

Sl.No.	Parameter	DJLIT			ALIS		
		2017	2018	2019	2017	2018	2019
1	Number of papers published	58	61	54	32	28	20
2	Number of citations received in the year of publication	26	33	23	11	6	4
3	Immediacy index	0.45	0.54	0.43	0.34	0.21	0.20

6. Conclusion

DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology and Annals of Library and Information Studies are the two leading LIS journals from India. A comparison of the two journals in terms of citations and calculated impact factor reveal that papers of DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology are more cited by others than the papers in Annals of Library and Information Studies. It is a matter of concern that Indian LIS journals have not been able to make an international mark and it is about time that the leading Indian LIS journals have made efforts to attain international stature.

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